

METROLOGICAL SERVICES IN THE FIELD OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY IN COMMUNICATION. INTERNATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS ON METROLOGY

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ABSTRACT: The existing structure of the system for ensuring unity is included: the ministry of information technologies and communications of the Republic of Uzbekistan is a basic metrological service for the cube union.uz Technical Committee for Standardization in the Field of Telecommunications and Postal Communications The State Inspection of Communications of Metrological Services and responsible for the state of measuring instruments of economic entities.

KEY WORDS: Standardization, certification system, Uzstandard agency, metrological service, telecommunications.

The system for ensuring the uniformity of measurements in the field of information technology and communication interacts with the state system for ensuring the uniformity of measurements in the state system of standardization by industry standardization and certification systems. The infraction of the system for ensuring the uniformity of measurements in the field of information technologies and communications with systems for ensuring the uniformity of measurements of other countries and international bodies is regulated in accordance with the current legislation by normative documents. The Uzstandard agency is entrusted with the functions of maintaining the state register of measuring instruments used in the sphere of state metrological control and supervision of maintaining the state register of standards for metrological provision, the state Register of Accredited Metrological Services and Metrology Laboratories agreeing organizational and methodological documents on the system for ensuring the uniformity of measurements in the field of communication and informatization of interaction with state systems for ensuring unity Rhenium other countries including the issues of mutual recognition of test results and type approval certificates of metrological certification and calibration procedure of measuring instruments of the state metrological control and supervision of the state of the measuring instruments. The Republican Center for Metrological Services provides state metrological control over:

1. Conducting tests to approve the type of measuring instruments.
2. Metrological certification of measuring instruments verification of measuring instruments.
3. Organization and conduct of accreditation of metrological services of the centers of the laboratory for the right to test and verify measuring instruments.

4. For methods of performing measurements and other specific types of metrological activity.

The Scientific and Research Institute for Standardization of Metrology and Certification provides training (retraining) of personal in established specialties and participates in the coordination of the developed industry normative documents on legal metrology examines the documents for the accreditation of metrological services and testing laboratories. The issues of metrological support in the sphere of communication and information are regulated and coordinated by the Ministry for the Development of Information Technologies and Communications of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The main functions of the Ministry of Information Technologies and Communication of the Republic of Uzbekistan:

- Organization of work on the formation of a system for ensuring the uniformity of measurements in the field of communication and information and coordination of activities and its participants in the interaction with the agency standard on the issues of legal metrology for attention and recognition of the type of measuring instruments;
- Interaction with the regional Commonwealth in the field of communications and other international organizations on the issues of development and harmonization of rules and norms the system for ensuring the uniformity of measurements in the sphere of communication and information is expensive;
- Addressing issues of a general sectoral nature and developing technical policy in ensuring the uniformity of measurements in the communications and information sector;
- Organization of work on the development of the legislative framework for metrological support of the sphere.

The basic metrological service carries out scientific and technical and organizational and methodological guidance for the implementation of the task of metrological support of economic entities in the field of communication and information. In accordance with the provision the basic metrological service maintains an industry register of measuring instruments annually updates the catalog of measuring instruments recommended for use in the communications and information industry. The sphere of communication and information is operated by metrological services at the radio communication center of broadcasting and television and in the branch of the joint – stock company at UZBECTELECOM. The State Inspection of Communications is the body of state control to ensure compliance with the requirements of legislative and regulatory acts of state and industry standards for license terms and the quality of services provided in the sphere of communication and information. The main functions of participants in the system for ensuring the uniformity of measurements in the field of communication and information are determined in accordance with the provisions on them agreed and approved in accordance with the established procedure.

MEK- the international electro technical commission is developing international standards for telecommunications devices for telecommunications television electrical engineering. MEK standards are used when exporting electromechanical and electronic equipment. The governing body is the Council of the International Electrotechnical Commission. The top position is president. It is elected every 3 years. The working languages of the MEK are Russian and English and French. Currently national committees 41 states are members of MEK. The international organization of legal metrology exists in 1956 and 50 states

cooperate in this field. The main tasks is to ensure the uniformity of measurements at the international level measurement method of measurement definition of terminology and conditions. The supreme body is the international conference which ensures the uniformity of measurements by the International Bureau of Measures and Libra. The OIML:

1. International Convention of Legal Metrology;
2. International Committee of Legal Metrology;
3. International Bureau of Legal Metrology;

In to the secretariat there is a Working group that prepares recommendations and coordinates. In 1992 in the CIS countries a council on metrology of standardization and certification was created, which deals with the problem of the elimination of technical barriers. Heads of the CIS countries on March 13, 1993 signed an agreement on the conduct of unified policy of the IPU and C.A number of agreements on a single regulatory framework for the development of the application of the results of certification of products and services between state standards and other regulatory documents have been signed. These agreements are being implemented in the CIS countries are discussed at meetings of national authorities. In the fund of interstate standards there are 19000 normative standards. Since 1992, more than 3800 interstate regulatory documents have been developed. They are coordinated by the members of the ISS taking in to account their normalization by international regional and advanced standards. This gives cooperation trade in economic and scientific and technical direction the removal of technical barriers and whether the promotion of productsto the international market of Europe.

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